

Eurodoc statement on the Scholars at Risk's Urgent appeal to European Governments and EU Institutions

[Urgent appeal to European Governments and EU Institutions: Take Action for Afghanistan's scholars, researchers, and civil society actors](#)

As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers and as a member of civil society, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc), a grassroots federation of 28 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 25 countries across Europe, is observing the terrible events unfolding in Afghanistan during the end of NATO's involvement in the region. We feel for our peers - young researchers and scholars, as well as other civil society actors and their families - whose lives are in immediate danger and whose basic rights are being taken away.

Academic freedom for a better world

As an ECRs' organisation, we advocate for a better future world - in the aspects of our safety, life stability, access to knowledge, career development and research. We do believe that protecting the academic freedom for present and future generations of scholars all over the world is crucial to shaping mutual understanding, contributing to scientific knowledge, and the advancement of society as a whole. These are the foundational values of the European Union and of the European common identity.

Ethical obligation to support

In light of these developments, we feel an ethical obligation to urge the EU institutions and the European governments to take action and support our endangered peers and all Afghan citizens that want to contribute to a progressive, pluralist vision of Afghanistan.

For this reason we approve and fully support the appeal issued by Scholars at Risk and already signed by a number of Higher Education Institutions, students and researchers' organisations.